

EFFECT OF AYURVEDA TREATMENT MODALITIES OF AMAVATA ON SIMPLE DISEASE ACTIVITY INDEX OF A SEROPOSITIVE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS CASE- A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic immune-mediated systemic inflammatory disease characterized by chronic synovial inflammation and hyperplasia, which drive joint erosion and damage, and a range of systemic manifestations, which contribute to overall disease burden. The cause for this manifestation is due to proinflammatory pathways which result in localized joint and systemic inflammation, which occur due to cytokines such as Interleukin-6 (IL-6), Interleukin-1 β etc. One function of IL-6 is to drive production of the acute-phase reactant following an inflammatory event. In *Ayurveda*, this Pathology can be explained with the *Amavata samprapti* where *Ama*, the morbid factor take seat in *Sandhi* such as *Hasta*, *Pada*, *Trika*, *Janu*, *Gulpha*, *Manya* etc., leading to pathological alteration in normal physiology of *Sandhi*. This presents with the major premonitory symptoms such as *Vrischika damshavat vedana* in *sandhi* (Severe pain), *Stabdha gatra* (stiffness in joints), *Sandhi shotha* (localised swelling), *Jwara* (rise in temperature) etc. It can be considered that *Ama* is the factor which is triggering

inflammatory mechanism in the *Sandhi* and is reflected in the form of raised inflammatory markers in the serum levels when tested in such cases. The above theory was verified by inculcating *Ayurveda* treatment modalities mentioned in *Amavata chikitsa* in a 39 year old female who was a known case of Seropositive Rheumatoid arthritis, was diagnosed as *Amavata* and treated with *Sadhyo Virechana* followed by *Vaitarana Basti* in *yoga basti* schedule with simultaneous oral administration of Tablet *Vyoshadi guggulu* 750mg 1 TID

after food for about 22 days. The outcome was assessed through Simple Disease Activity Index of the subject before and after the intervention as stated. Results showed a significant remission in the disease activity of the subject.

KEYWORDS: *Ama*, Auto-immune joint disorders, Inflammatory markers, *Sadhyovirechana*, *Vaitarana Basti*, *Vyoshadi Guggulu*.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease of unknown aetiology marked by a symmetric, peripheral polyarthritis. It is the most common form of chronic inflammatory arthritis and often results in joint damage and physical disability.^[1] It is an autoimmune disease of insidious onset and unknown aetiology afflicting 1% of the adult population, women more than men. RA can affect any joint, but it is common to find involvement of the metacarpophalangeal (MCP), proximal interphalangeal (PIP) joints of the fingers, the interphalangeal joints of the thumbs, the wrists, the knees, and the metatarsophalangeal (MTP) joints of the toes. The affected joints are swollen and tender. The axial skeleton is usually spared except for the cervical spine. Malaise, morning stiffness, and fatigue are common.^[2] The aetiology of RA is not completely understood; however, it is known that a complex interaction between genetic and environmental factors induces a pathological activation of the immune system, leading to the clinical onset of RA.^[3] Numerous studies highlighted a critical role of the gut microbiota in RA pathogenesis, through mechanisms including mainly production of proinflammatory metabolites, impairment of the intestinal mucosal barrier, and molecular mimicry of autoantigens.^[4] Molecular mimicry is a mechanism by which pathogen derived antigens that share sequence homology with self-peptides may lead to cross-activation of autoreactive T or B cells, triggering autoimmunity.^[5]

Similar disease presentation of RA is correlated to *Amavata* as per classical references of the *Ayurveda* texts, where 'Ama' is a prime innate factor of the pathogenesis. In the aetiopathogenesis of *Amavata* major importance is given to *Viruddhanna Cheshta* leading to *mandagni* in turn leading to *Dushita Annavaha and Rasavaha Srotas*.^[6] Further manifests in '*Hasta-Pada-Shiro-Gulpha-Trika-Janu Sandhi*' and clinically presents in the form of *Ruja* (Pain), *Shotha* (Swelling), *Stabdha gatra* (Stiffness in joints), *Agni dourbalya* (reduced appetite) etc. as the exacerbated form of this condition.^[7] *Chikitsa* in this condition is always focused in correction of *mandagni*, which includes, *Langhana*, *Tikta-Katu- Deepana Dravya prayoga as Aushadhi* and *Anna Pana* to tackle *Jatharagnimandyata*. *Ruksha Swedana*,

Virechana, Kshara Basti with saindhavadya Anuvasana to tackle Srotodushti and Dhatwagnimandya at the level of Dhatu.^[8]

In *Amavata, Vaitarana Basti* which is one among the different variants of *Kshara Basti* said to be *Shoola-Anaha-Amavatahara*.^[9] It had also shown to be significant in counter acting against *Ama* (innate pathological factor), *Shula* (Pain) and *Shotha Avastha* (inflammatory phase) according to the various studies published on the same.^[10]

CASE REPORT

A 39 year old married female who is a home maker from Bengaluru came to the *Kayachikitsa* OPD of SDMIAH, Bengaluru during May 2023 with complaints of pain in bi-lateral Shoulder, Elbow, Knee and Small Joints of hands since 1.5 years. It was associated with stiffness in the small joints during early morning since 1.5years and weight gain of 5 kg in 3 months. The condition was progressive in nature with frequent episodes of exacerbations on exposure to cold weather and travelling. During such episode intake of oral NSAIDs, application of hot packs and topical analgesic creams would relieve her symptoms. But repeated episodes gradually affected her normal daily routine activities. Due to the worsening of the symptoms expecting a cure she approached *Kayachikitsa* out-patient department of SDMIAH, Bengaluru. She had no history of other major systemic illness or family history contributing to the current complaints. Her menstrual history appeared normal with an uneventful obstetric history. Her personal history revealed that she is a vegetarian with increased consumption of coffee (4-5 times/day) and a sedentary life style. Her appetite was slightly reduced with regular bowel movement and urine output. Sleep habits appeared regular.

Clinical Findings

- General examination- Vital signs had no deviation except with a BMI of 32.41 Kg/m². And all other general findings appeared normal except signs of oedema at few involved joints.
- Systemic examination- All other systemic examinations appeared normal except in Locomotory system, where findings are mentioned in Table No. 1 and involved joint assessment is depicted in Table No. 2.

Table No. 1: Locomotory System Examination (GALS screening).

Parameters	Findings
Gait	Normal swing and stance phase noted
Deformities	No joint deformities noted
Range of movement	No restricted range of movement except painful during an attempt to fold
Tenderness	Noted in 21 joints out of 28
Swelling	Noted in 8 joints out of 28

Table No. 2: Joint Involvement.

Joint	Left		Right	
	Tender	Swollen	Tender	Swollen
Shoulder	+	+	+	-
Elbow	+	-	+	+
Wrist	+	-	+	-
MCP 1	+	-	-	-
MCP 4	+	-	-	-
MCP 5	+	+	-	-
PIP 1	+	+	+	+
PIP 2	+	-	+	+
PIP 3	+	-	+	+
PIP 4	+	-	+	+
PIP 5	+	-	+	-
Knee	+	-	+	-
	Tender- 21/28		Swollen- 8/28	

- Laboratory findings of blood serum (as on 2023 May 13)- Haemoglobin percentage- 10.2 g%, R. A. Factor- 72 IU/mL, C.R.P.- 5.6mg/L, E.S.R.- 45 mm/hg.

Diagnosis

- Based on her history and presence of lakshanas such as *ruja* in *Janu*, *Bahu*, *Kurpara* and *Parva sandhi* (Pain in shoulder, Knee, Elbow and small joints) associated with *shotha* (Swelling), *gauravata* (heaviness of the body), *gatra stabdhata* (Stiffness), *utrasahani* (lassitude), *agni dourbalya* (reduced appetite), *trishna* (Thirst); she was diagnosed as *Amavata* where the subject presents with major *pratyatma lakshanas* (predominant symptoms) as mentioned in the classical texts.
- 2010 American college of Rheumatology (ACR)/ European league against Rheumatism (EULAR) Classification criteria for Rheumatoid Arthritis¹¹ was done to classify the condition according to the symptomatology. In this case the score of 8 out of 10 was noted, satisfying the criteria to diagnose as RA. Simple disease activity index (SDAI)^[12] of RA was assessed to evaluate the severity of the disease activity in the subject resulted

in a score of 43.56 out of 86 which falls in the category of high disease activity during initial assessment.

Therapeutic Intervention

She was treated as In-patient for a period of 10 days at SDMIAH, Bengaluru. Based on the clinical findings exhibited it was considered that she was in an inflammatory phase i.e., *Ama avastha*. Hence a protocol consisting of initial *Amahara chikitsa* with *Koshta shodhana* followed by *Srotomula chikitsa* in the form of *Vaitarana Basti* in *Yoga basti* schedule (Table No. 3) was planned which included 3 *Vaitarana Basti* (Decoction enema) with 5 *Anuvasana basti* (Oil enema) alternatively on consecutive days starting and ending with *Anuvasana basti* respectively. She was also simultaneously administered with one tablet of *Vyoshadi guggulu*^[13] 750 mg three times in a day after food with warm water orally from the day 1 of *basti* schedule till her follow up. She was strictly instructed to follow *Pathya ahara* and *vihara* (wholesome diet and regimen) till her follow up. The chronological order of the treatment protocol was implemented as mentioned in Table No. 4.

Table No. 3: Yoga basti schedule with Ingredients of Vaitarana Basti.^[9]

Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8
AB	VB	AB	VB	AB	VB	AB	AB
AB- Anuvasana basti				VB- Vaitarana Basti			
Ingredients		Quantity		Ingredients		Quantity	
1) <i>Bruhat Saindhavadya Taila</i> ^[14]		80mL		1) <i>Saindhava Lavana</i> (Rock Salt)		12g	
				2) <i>Guda</i> (Jaggery)		24g	
				3) <i>Chincha</i> (<i>Tamarindus indica</i>)		48g	
				4) <i>Ushna Jala</i> (Hot water) [for <i>chincha</i> and <i>guda paka</i>]		200mL	
				5) <i>Moorchita Taila</i>		80mL	
				6) <i>Go mutra</i>		100mL	
Total: 80mL				Total: 464mL			

Table No. 4: Chronology of the Treatment protocol from Day of admission till follow up.

DATE/ DAY	TREATMENTS
12.05.2023 Day-1 (Day on admission)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>Sarvanga valuka sweda</i> ✓ <i>Sarvanga Dhanyamladhara</i> Orally, Tab. <i>Chitrakadi vati</i> 2-2-2 before food with warm water.
13.05.2023 Day- 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>Sadhyovirechana</i> with <i>Gandharva Hastadi Taila</i>- 80mL with 100mL warm milk ✓ Total No. of <i>vegas</i> attained- 8
14.05.2023 to 21.05.2023 Day 3 to Day 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>Sarvanga Valuka Sweda</i> ✓ <i>Sarvanga Dhanyamladhara</i> ✓ <i>Vaitarana Basti</i> in <i>Yoga Basti</i> Schedule <i>Anuvasana Basti-Bruhat Saidhavadya Taila</i> (80ml) ✓ Orally, Tab. <i>Vyoshadi Guggulu</i> 750mg 1-1-1 after food with warm water
Day of Discharge 22.05.2023 Day 11	DISCHARGE ADVISE, 1. Tab. <i>Vyoshadi Guggulu</i> 750mg 1-1-1 after food with warm water for 15 days. 2. Strict <i>pathya ahara</i> and <i>vihara</i> . 3. To review after 15 days.
Follow up 06.06.2023- Day 26 (Day of assessment)	

Patient Assessment

Simple Disease Activity Index (S.D.A.I) score and Serum R. A. Factor was calculated as a primary outcome measures before the treatment on Day 1; the second assessment was done on the Day 26 during follow up.

OUTCOME AND RESULTS

S. D. A. I. score was 32.08 out of 80 during final assessment (Day 26) which was 45.56 out of 80 during initial assessment (Day 1). Though disease activity falls at high activity, there was a difference of 11.48 in the score observed. Serum R.A. Factor which is an autoantibody specific to auto-immune mechanism in RA reduced from 72 IU/mL to 11.06mL respectively. There was also reduction in the score of tender joints and swollen joints from 21 to 15 out of 28 and 8 to 4 out of 28 respectively. (Table No. 5).

Table No. 5: Simple Disease Activity Index (S.D.A.I) Chart on Day 1 and Day 26 respectively.

Sl. No.	Day 1 (12.05.2023)	Day 26 (06.06.2023)
1.	Tender joint score (28) 21	Tender joint score (28) 15
2.	Swollen joint score (28) 8	Swollen joint score (28) 4
3.	Patient global assessment of Disease activity (!) 8	Patient global assessment of Disease activity (10) 7
4.	Provider global assessment of Disease activity (!) 6	Provider global assessment of Disease activity (10) 5.5
5.	Serum C. R. P. (mg/dL) (10) 0.56	Serum C. R. P. (mg/dL) (10) 0.58
Total Score- 43.56/ 86		Total Score- 32.08/ 86 ↓

DISCUSSION

Assessing the current case, 'Ama' which can be considered as the innate part of the autoimmune process triggering the condition. After correction of 'Agni' at the level of both *Jatharaagni* and *Dhathwagni* through mentioned protocol, there was a significant change in the presentation of the symptoms. Where.

- Initial *Agni deepana* and *Amahara* treatments such as *Sarvanga valuka sweda*^[15] (Hot sand Pottali fomentation) having qualities of *ushna*, *ruksha* and *laghu* helped in *Amaharana* and *Shothahara* action, whereas *Sarvanga dhanyamladhara*^[16] (Decoction bath with *Dhanyamla*) having *amla rasa*, *Laghu*, *teekshna*, *guna* with *Vata-kaphahara karma* helped in *Shulahara* and *Shothahara* action along with relieving *stabdhata*.
- *Sadhyovirechana* helped in *Vruddha Doshavasechana* in the *koshta* to facilitate proper absorption of planned *Basti karma*.
- *Vaitarana Basti* due to its *teekshnata* attributed in enhancing *Agni* at the level of *srotas* further induced *Amapachana* at the level of *Dhatus* yielding to remission of the inflammatory mechanism. Wherein *Bruhat Saindhavadya anuvasana*^[14] specifically indicated in *Amavata* consisting *Eranda Taila* and other contents having *ushna*, *vata-kaphashamaka* resulting in *vedanasthapana* and *shothahara* (Anti-inflammatory action). It also mitigates the vitiation of *Vata* due to *teekshnata* of *vaitarana basti* administration and helps in *vatanulomana*.
- Tablet *Vyoshadi guggulu* consists of *Haritaki*, *Amalaki*, *Vibhitaki*, *Pippali*, *Maricha*, *Shunti*, *Musta*, *Chitra* and *Vidanga* together with equal quantity of *Shodhita guggulu*.^[13] It majorly possesses *Tikta-katu pradhana rasa* with *deepana karma* inducing *Amapachana* at the level of *Jatharaagni* further yielding in management of *ruja* and *shotha* even after *Basti chikitsa* which prevents the progression of the condition.

- *Pathya ahara* and *vihara* helps in maintaining the normal gut metabolism without any susceptibility to the triggering factors.
- Hence it can be considered that the *Sadhyovirechana* followed by *Vaitarana Basti* attempts in correcting the gut dysbiosis occurred in the pathogenesis of *Amavata*, while Tablet *Vyoshadi guggulu* with *Pathya ahara* and *vihara* prevents the progression by maintaining the normal gut metabolism which might have helped to reduce the local joint inflammatory mechanism indirectly resulting in remission in the values of Simple Disease Activity Index of the subject.

CONCLUSION

Reduction in the score of 11.48 falls at moderate response^[17] to the current intervention. Hence, the above stated treatment protocols of *Amavata* adopted in the current case of Rheumatoid arthritis showed a significant remission in the Simple disease activity index and reduction in the Serum R. A. Factor levels of the subject.

Further extension of duration of the treatment protocol is needed to bring about major remission in the disease activity of the current case. It requires to be tested on a larger sample size for a definitive conclusion to establish a standard *Ayurveda* treatment protocol on the same.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written informed consent from the patient was obtained to publish details of the case.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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